

RESULTS OF USING CORPORATE TRAINING IN THE FORMATION OF AFFILIATION MOTIVATION IN ADOLESCENTS

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ANNOTATION

This article examines the results of using corporate training in the formation of affiliation motivation in adolescents.

Key words: *Motive, affiliation, psychological research, program effectiveness, corporate training, measurement, detection, study, B.G. Ananyev, K.K. Platonov, E.V. Shorokhova, V.S. Merlin, L.S. Vygotsky, L.I. Boyovich, A.V. Filipov, A.V. Petrovsky G.M. Andreeva, V.V. Ktolin.*

The development and implementation of a program for developing affiliative motivation in adolescents is of great importance in increasing the effectiveness of learning. Based on the scientific results and conclusions obtained during our research, we were able to create a “model of the formation of the affiliation motive in adolescents.”

The motive for affiliation in adolescents is, first of all, the desire for cooperation, the process of striving for the effective use of the volume of communicative capabilities, therefore it is inevitable that the systematic study and development of this process is considered one of the important tasks of society, ensuring the development of the individual. In general, research devoted to the understanding, explanation and scientific substantiation of the affiliation motive in adolescents and, at the same time, important for determining the tasks of the affiliation motive, can be divided into certain areas. After all, researchers from each direction analyze the motive of affiliation, which

is important for the development of a teenager, based on one or another idea, and draw appropriate conclusions. When conducting our research, we to a certain extent accepted the scientific and theoretical conclusions noted in these areas as a methodological basis.

1. Determination of the motive for affiliation of adolescents not only as a complex of individual psychological processes, but also as a social-subjective being consisting of an integral system (B.G. Ananyev, K.K. Platonov, E.V. Shorokhova, V.S. Merlin) etc.), in which each teenager is considered and explained as a set of common actions aimed at individual and social development. In a certain sense, this theory presupposes the need to develop a set of methods aimed at studying the determination of harmony in the development of personality and activity on the basis of a certain hierarchical system.

2. Exploring the motive of belonging as a product of the individual's relationship to the social environment and needs, all "external" social stimuli serve to manifest, or rather develop, the "internal" psychological potential of the individual. That is why a person actively interacts with an objective being (L.S. Vygotsky, L.I. Boyovich, A.V. Filipov, A.V. Petrovsky). In this case, an important management role is played by a person's interpersonal relationships, his behavior, and all psychological processes that affect the effective course of life.

3. The motive of belonging is considered as a product of ensuring and developing the effectiveness of the individual psychological process (E.A. Golubeva, V.D. Nebilitsyn, E.A. Klimov, N.S. Leites, B.R. Kadyrov, V.A. Bogdanov, B.M. Teplov, etc.). At the same time, the activity of a teenager is studied not only on the basis of the development of social, but also on the basis of the development of pedagogical and psychological characteristics, and at the same time it is recognized that activity is the basis for the manifestation of the personality and intellectual development of adolescents. Our scientific, practical and empirical conclusions related to the study of the process of adolescent activity according to the criteria of the motive of belonging are based on the methodological principles of this direction.

4. Interpretation of the activities of adolescents as a process based on socio-psychological directions and having an emotional and motivational status (G.M. Andreeva, V.V. Ktolin, A.A. Bodalov, V.S. Merlin, Ya.N. Kolominsky, I.S. Kon, E.A. Anufriev, L.I. Antsiferova, G'.B. Shumarov, V.A. Tokareva, A.A. Faizullaev) while the product of individual activity represents various socio-historical and socio-psychological aspects understood and studied based on high levels of behavioral and affiliative motivation in the conditions.

5. In our study, we studied that the motivation to belong among adolescents occupies one of the leading places in their activities and formation. Each level of the motive of belonging is associated with the degree of formation of adolescents' social ideas and their adequate reflection in interpersonal relationships, that is, compliance with the phenomenon in reality.

Currently, there is no doubt that healthy adolescents have a stable psychological state and adequate motivation. At the moment, the scientific substantiation of the origin of such motives, the study of the dynamics of their development and influence on the effectiveness of the activity process, using specific scientific methods, the enrichment of modern psychology with scientific and theoretical information is one of the important tasks. today's psychology.

As we have already noted above, analysis of indicators of the affiliation motive and paying serious attention to its specific socio-psychological factors are important in ensuring the socio-psychological development of a teenager. In addition, it is natural that regional and age factors play a role in this process. From this point of view, in order to obtain detailed information about the indicators of the affiliation motive characteristic of adolescents and its possibilities, as well as the possibilities of psychological defense at the beginning and end of adolescence, separate studies were conducted in adolescents. The task was set to collect empirical data and analyze their results taking into account socio-psychological requirements. This paragraph intends to describe the analysis of empirical data obtained by introducing additional scientific clarifications on this issue.

Of course, it is difficult to fully cover the range of indicators of the affiliation motive within the framework of one study. However, we tried to study and analyze the indicators of the affiliation motive based on the criteria of the affiliation motive, which we previously adopted based on the purpose of the study, draw appropriate conclusions and give practical recommendations.

Based on these theoretical and experimentally substantiated scientific principles, the activities of adolescents (grades 5, 9) studying in rural and urban secondary schools were studied.

Each result obtained was entered into a system of criteria and points, adopted in a special manner, allowing one to have the following information:

- Determination of the process of affiliation motive in adolescents and the factors influencing it.
- Determination of the levels of the motive of belonging in various social situations among adolescents.
- Assessment of personality traits associated with a teenager's motive for belonging.
- Assessing the motivation of adolescents based on emotional intelligence, empathy and self-confidence, which underlie emotional self-esteem.
- Determination of directions specific to the individual capabilities of a teenager and behavioral motivation for the formation of the motive of belonging.
- Assessing the influence of dynamic characteristics, social maturity, social courage, emotional stability, sociability, emotional instability on the indicators of the motive of belonging in the personality of a teenager.
- Explain the socio-psychological harmony between the motive of belonging and the speech, communicative, interpersonal relationships of a teenager, etc.

Each result obtained in these directions was combined and studied in a general manner, based on a single goal of the study.

All oral and written information received from respondents was processed in accordance with the purpose of the study.

Also, during the course of our research, the following tasks were solved in the relevant chapters:

1. Since the object of the study was carried out within the framework of relevant psychological factors, it was taken into account that the formation of affiliation motivation specific to each teenager, considered as an object of study, depends on the propensity to communicate, emotional stability, attitude, social maturity and self-control factors that directly influence him.
2. All 5th and 9th graders who participated in the study were combined into one group to facilitate the analysis of the obtained empirical data.
3. When analyzing indicators of the general motive of belonging, each teenager and his activity were recorded. Particular attention was paid to the pedagogical and psychological relationships between a group of adolescents suitable for the purpose of the study.

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